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MODULATION OF GASTRO-INTESTINAL TRANSIT TIME BY FLOATING DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Floating drug delivery system (FDDS) design appear to be one of the most effective and rational approaches for controlled oral drug delivery. The scientific and patent literature shows increased interest in academics and industrial research groups regarding the novel dosage forms that can be retained in the stomach for prolonged and predictable period of time. One of the most feasible approaches for achieving a prolonged and predictable drug delivery profiles in the gastrointestinal tract is to control the gastric residence time, using gastro retentive dosage forms that will provide us with new and important therapeutic options. From the formulation and technological point of view, the floating drug delivery system is considerably easy and logical approach. Floating drug delivery system enable prolonged and continuous input of the drug to the upper part of the gastro retention tract and improve the bioavailability of medication that is characterized by a narrow absorption window. An attempt has been made in this review article to introduce the readers to the current technological developments in floating drug delivery.

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INTRODUCTION

Floating drug delivery systems are retained in the stomach and are useful for drugs that are poorly soluble or unstable in intestinal fluid. Oral administration is the most convenient and preferred means of any drug delivery to the systemic circulation. The reason that the oral route achieved such popularity may be in part attributes to its ease of administration.¹ Oral controlled drug delivery system is complicated by limited gastric residence time (GRTs). Fast GI transit prevents complete drug release in the absorption zone and reduces the efficacy of the administered dose since the majority of drugs are absorbed in stomach or the upper part of small intestine.^{2,3} To overcome these limitations, various approaches have been proposed to increase gastric residence of drug delivery system in the upper part of the gastrointestinal tract includes floating drug dosage system (FDDS), swelling or expanding system and other delayed gastric emptying devices. Among these systems, FDDS have been most commonly used.

Floating drug delivery system

Floating drug delivery system have a bulk density less than that of gastric fluids and so remain buoyant in the stomach without affecting the gastric emptying rate for a prolong period of time. While the system is floating on the gastric contents, the drug is released slowly at the desired rate from the system. After release of drug, the residual system is emptied from the stomach. This result in an increased GRT and a better control of fluctuation in plasma drug concentration. However, beside a minimal gastric content needed to allow the proper achievement of the buoyancy retention principle, a minimal level of floating force (F) is also required to keep the dosage form reliably buoyant on the surface of meal. To measure the floating force equivalent to F (as a function of time) that is required to maintain the submerged object. The object floats better if RW is on the higher positive side. This apparatus helps in optimizing FDDS with respect to stability and durability of floating forces produced in order to prevent the drawbacks of unforeseeable intragastric buoyancy capability variation.⁴

$$RW \text{ or } F = F_{(\text{buoyancy})} - F_{(\text{gravity})} \\ = (D_f - D_s) gV$$

Where RW = total vertical force, D_f = fluid density, D_s = object density, V = volume and g = acceleration due to gravity.

Fig-1: Mechanism of floating systems, GF= Gastric fluid

Biological aspects of GRDFs

The successful development of oral controlled drug delivery systems requires an understanding of the three aspects of the system, namely

1. The physiochemical characteristics of the drug
2. Anatomy and physiology of GIT and Characteristics of Dosage

Stomach Anatomy

The main function of the stomach is to process and transport food. It serves as a short-term storage reservoir, allowing a rather large meal to be consumed quickly. Substantial enzymatic digestion is initiated in stomach, particularly of proteins. Vigorous contractions of gastric smooth muscle mix and grind foodstuffs with gastric secretions, resulting in liquefaction of food. As food is liquefied in the stomach, it is slowly released into the small intestine for further processing.⁵

Fig-2: Anatomy of Stomach

Stomach anatomy

Anatomically the stomach is divided into 3 regions: fundus, body, and antrum (pylorus). The

proximal part made of fundus and body acts as a reservoir for undigested material, whereas the antrum is the main site for mixing motions and act as a pump for gastric emptying by propelling actions.

It has been reported that the mean value of pH in fasted healthy subjects is 1.1 ± 0.15 . But when food comes into the stomach, the pH may rise to levels in the 3.0 to 4.0 level due to the buffering capacity of proteins. However, in fasted state, basal gastric secretion in women is slightly lower than that of men. Gastric emptying occurs during fasting as well as fed states. The pattern of motility is however distinct in the 2 states. During the fasting state an inter digestive series of electrical events take place, which cycle both through stomach and intestine every 2 to 3 hours.

This is called the interdigestive myoelectric cycle or migrating myoelectric cycle (MMC), which is further divided into following 4 phases.⁶

1. Phase I (Basal phase) lasts from 30 to 60 minutes with rare contractions.
2. Phase II (Preburst phase) lasts for 20 to 40 minutes with intermittent action potential and contractions. As the phase progresses the intensity and frequency also increases gradually.
3. Phase III (burst phase) lasts for 10 to 20 minutes. It includes intense and regular contractions for short period. It is due to this wave that all the undigested material is swept out of the stomach down to the small intestine. It is also known as the housekeeper wave.
4. Phase IV lasts for 0 to 5 minutes and occurs between phases III and I of 2 consecutive cycles

Fig-3: Motility pattern in GIT

Table-1: Transit time (TT) of different dosage forms across the segments of GI tract

1.1.1.1 Dosage form	Transit time (h)		
	Gastric	Small intestine	Total
Tablets	2.7±1.5	3.1±0.4	5.8
Pellets	1.2±1.3	3.4±1.0	4.6
Capsules	0.8±1.2	3.2±0.8	4.0
Oral solution	0.3±0.07	4.1±0.5	4.4

REQUIREMENTS FOR GASTRIC RETENTION

The physiological factors in the stomach must be noted to achieve gastric retention. The dosage must be able to withstand the forces caused by peristaltic waves in the stomach and the constant contractions and grinding and churning mechanisms. To function as a gastric retention device, it must resist premature gastric emptying.

Factors affecting Gastric retention

The gastric retention time (GRT) of dosage form is controlled by several factors that affect their efficacy as a gastro retentive system.

Density – GRT is a function of dosage form buoyancy that is dependent on the density. A density of less than 1.0 gm/cm³ is required to exhibit floating property.⁷

Size – Dosage form units with a diameter of more than 7.5mm are reported to have an increased GRT compared with those with diameter of 9.9mm.

Shape of dosage form – Tetrahedron and ring-shaped devices with a flexural modulus of 48 and 22.5 kilo pounds per square inch (KSI) are reported to have better GRT, 90% to 100% retention at 24 hours compared with other shapes.⁸

Single or multiple unit formulation – Multiple unit formulations show a more predictable release profile and insignificant impairing of performance due to failure of units, allow co administration of units with different release profiles or containing incompatible substances and permit a larger margin of safety against dosage form failure compared with single unit dosage forms.

Fed or unfed state – Under fasting conditions, the GI motility is characterized by periods of strong motor activity or the migrating myoelectric complex (MMC) that occurs every 1.5 to 2 hours.

The MMC sweeps undigested material from the stomach and, if the timing of administration of the formulation coincides with that of the MMC, the GRT of the unit can be expected to be very short. However, in the fed state, MMC is delayed and GRT is considerably longer.⁹

Nature of meal – Feeding of indigestible polymers or fatty acid salts can change the motility pattern of the stomach to a fed state, thus decreasing the gastric emptying rate and prolonging drug release.¹⁰

Caloric content – GRT can be increased by 4 to 10 hours with a meal that is high in proteins and fats.¹⁰

Frequency of feed – The GRT can increase by over 400 minutes when successive meals are given compared with a single meal due to the low frequency of MMC.⁹

Gender – Mean ambulatory GRT in males (3.4±0.6 hours) is less compared with their age and race-matched female counter parts (4.6±1.2 hours), regardless of the weight, height and body surface.

Age – Elderly people, especially those over 70, have a significantly longer GRT.

Posture – GRT can vary between supine and upright ambulatory states of the patient.

Concomitant drug administration – Anti cholinergics like Atropine and Propantheline, Opiates like Codeine and Prokinetic agents like Metoclopramide and Cisapride.

Biological factors – Diabetes and Crohn's disease

Formulation considerations for GRDDS

- 1) Must have effective retention in the stomach to suit for the clinical demand
- 2) Must be convenient for intake to facilitate patient compliance

- 3) Must have sufficient drug loading capacity
- 4) Must control the drug release profile
- 5) Must have full degradation and evacuation of the system once the drug release is over
- 6) Should not have effect on gastric motility including emptying pattern.

APPROACHES TO GASTRIC RETENTION

Several approaches have been developed to extend gastrointestinal transit time by prolonging the residence time of drug in the stomach.¹¹

- A) Hydrodynamically balanced systems (HBS)
- B) Gas generating systems
- C) Rate forming systems
- D) Low density systems

A. Hydrodynamically balanced systems (HBS)

Single unit dosage form contains one or more gel forming hydrophilic polymers. On coming in contact with gastric fluids the hydrocolloid in the system hydrates and forms colloidal gel barrier around the gel surface. The air entrapped by the swollen polymer maintains the density less than unity and confers the buoyancy to the dosage form.¹² Commonly used excipients are hydroxyl propylcellulose, hydroxyl propyl methylcellulose.

B. Gas generating systems

Floation achieved by filling a mixture of sodium alginate and sodium bicarbonate and floating property is due to the generation of CO₂ that was trapped in the hydrating gel network on exposure to an acidic environment.

C. Rate forming systems

Formulation contains gel forming solution of sodium alginate, carbonates or bicarbonates swells and forms a viscous cohesive gel by the entrapment of CO₂ bubbles on contact with gastric fluids. Formulation also contains antacids such as aluminum hydroxide or calcium carbonate to reduce gastric acidity.

D. Low density systems

The system is made of low density materials. Gas generating systems inevitably have a lag time

before floating on stomach contents during which the dosage may undergo premature evacuation through the pyloric sphincter. Therefore low density system (<1gm/cm³) with immediate buoyancy have been developed. These techniques used to prepare hollow microspheres which involve simple solvent evaporation or solvent diffusion methods. Polycarbonates, Eudragits, Cellulose acetate, calcium alginate, agar and low methoxylated pectin are commonly used polymers. Buoyancy and drug release are dependent on quantity of polymer, plasticizer, polymer ratio, and solvent used.¹³⁻¹⁶

Formulation of device must comply with the following criteria

1. It must have sufficient structure to form a cohesive gel barrier.
2. It must maintain an overall specific gravity lower than that of gastric contents (1.004-1.010).
- 3 It should dissolve slowly enough to serve as a drug reservoir.

Types of floating drug delivery systems

Based on the mechanism of buoyancy and two distinctly different technologies have been utilized in the development of FDDS.

- 1) Non- Effervescent FDDS
- 2) Effervescent FDDS

1) Non-Effervescent FDDS

The Non-effervescent FDDS is based on mechanism of swelling of polymer or bioadhesion to mucosal layer in GI tract. Capsule/tablet contains a mixture of drug and hydrocolloids. Upon contact with gastric fluid, the mixture swells and forms a gelatinous barrier thereby remaining buoyant in the gastric juice for an extended period of time.

The most commonly used excipients are gel forming or highly swellable cellulose type hydrocolloids, hydrophilic gums, polysaccharides and matrix forming materials such as polycarbonate, polyacrylate, polymethacrylate, polystyrene as well as bioadhesive polymers such as Chitosan and carbopol

Fig-4: Working Principle of Non-Effervescent Type of FDDS

A. Single Layer Floating Tablets

These are formulated by a) intimate mixing of drug with a gel-forming hydrocolloid. b) Intimate mixing of drug with low-density enteric materials such as CAP, HPMC which swells in contact with gastric fluid and maintains bulk density of less than GI fluids.

B. Bi-layer Floating Tablets

Bilayer tablet contains one immediate release layer and one sustained release layer. After the initial dose is delivered by immediate release layer, the sustained release layer absorbs the gastric fluid and forms a colloidal gel barrier on its surface and produces a bulk density of less than that of GI fluid and remains buoyant in the stomach for an extended period of time.

2) Effervescent FDDS

Effervescent systems involves the use of effervescent components like Sodium bicarbonate and citric acid and tartaric acid along with the polymers like methocel, or polysaccharides like chitosan or matrix containing portion of liquid that gasify and evaporates at body temperature. The matrices are fabricated in such a manner that upon arrival in stomach, carbon dioxide is liberated by acidity of gastric contents and is entrapped in the gellified hydrocolloid, produces an upward movement of the dosage form and maintains its buoyancy. A decrease in specific gravity causes the dosage form to float on the chyme.

1. Gas generating systems

Floating capsules Floating capsules are prepared by filling with a mixture of sodium alginate and sodium bicarbonate and have floating property due to generation of CO_2 that was trapped in the hydrating gel network on exposure to an acidic environment.

Multiple unit type floating pills

The system consists of sustained release pills as 'seeds' surrounded by double layers. The inner layer consists of effervescent agents while the outer layer is of swellable membrane layer. Containing mainly PVA & purified shellac effervescent, direct contact between sodium bicarbonate comprised the inner layer and tartaric acid the outer layer, after immersed in dissolution medium at body temp, it sank at once and then forms swollen pills like balloons, which float as they have lower density. This lower density is due to generation and entrapment of CO_2 within the system. The system was found to float completely within 10 min and approximately 80% remained floating over a period of 5 hr irrespective of PH and viscosity of medium.

2. Volatile Liquid / Vacuum Containing Systems

A. Intra-gastric floating gastrointestinal drug delivery system

These systems can be made to float in the stomach because of floatation chamber, which

may be filled with air or a vacuum or harmless gas, while drug reservoir is encapsulated inside a micro-porous compartment.

Fig-5: Intra-gastric floating gastrointestinal drug delivery system

B. Inflatable gastrointestinal delivery systems

In these systems an inflatable chamber is incorporated, which contains liquid ether that gasifies at body temperature to cause the chamber to inflate in the stomach. The inflatable chamber with a drug reservoir is encapsulated in a gelatin capsule. After oral administration, the capsule dissolves to release the drug reservoir together with the inflatable chamber. The inflatable chamber automatically inflates and retains the drug reservoir compartment in the stomach. The drug continuously released from the reservoir into the gastric fluid.

Fig-7: Intragastric osmotically controlled drug delivery system.

Fig-6:Inflatable gastrointestinal delivery system.

C. Intra-gastric Osmotically controlled drug delivery system

Comprises of an osmotic pressure controlled drug delivery device and an inflatable floating support in a biodegradable capsule. In the stomach, the capsule disintegrates to release the intra-gastric osmotically controlled drug delivery device. The inflatable support inside forms a deformable hollow polymeric bag that contains a liquid that gasifies at body temperature to inflate the bag. The osmotic pressure controlled drug delivery device consists of two components; drug reservoir compartment and an osmotically active compartment. The drug reservoir compartment is enclosed by a pressure responsive collapsible bag, which is impermeable to vapour and liquid and has a drug delivery orifice. The osmotically active compartment contains an osmotically active salt and is enclosed within a semi permeable housing. In the stomach, the water in the GI fluid is continuously absorbed through the semi permeable membrane into osmotically active compartment to dissolve the osmotically active salt. The osmotic pressure thus created acts on the collapsible bag and in turn forces the drug reservoir compartment to reduce its volume and activate drug release through the delivery orifice.

The floating support is also made to contain a bioerodible plug that erodes after a predetermined time to deflate the support. The deflated drug delivery system is then emptied from the stomach.

Advantages of FDOS ¹⁷

1. Improved drug absorption, because of increased GRT and more time spent by the dosage form at its absorption site.
2. Controlled delivery of drugs.
3. Delivery of drugs for local action in the stomach.
4. Minimizing the mucosal irritation due to drugs, by drug releasing slowly at controlled rate.
5. Treatment of gastrointestinal disorders such as gastro-esophageal reflux.
6. Simple and conventional equipment for manufacture.
7. Ease of administration and better patient compliance.
8. Site-specific drug delivery.

pharmacological effects with minimum side effects.

Disadvantages of FDSS

1. Gastric retention is influenced by many factors such as gastric motility, pH and presence of food. These factors are never constant and hence the buoyancy cannot be predicted.
2. Drugs that cause irritation and lesion to gastric mucosa are not suitable to be formulated as floating drug delivery systems.
3. High variability in gastric emptying time due to its all or non-emptying process.
4. Gastric emptying of floating forms in supine subjects may occur at random and becomes highly dependent on the diameter and size. Therefore patients should not be dosed with floating forms just before going to bed.

CONCLUSION

The literature searched during the review of the topic revolved that Gastro-retentive floating drug delivery systems have emerged as an efficient means of enhancing the bioavailability and controlled delivery of many drugs. The increasing sophistication of delivery technology will ensure the development of increase number of gastro retentive drug delivery to optimize the delivery of molecules that exhibit narrow absorption window, low bioavailability and extensive first pass metabolism. At present research work in the field of gastro retentive drug delivery various novel approaches and techniques have been used successfully by various researchers and find their way to the market. Many formulations are used in the treatment of patients by the physician and showing good

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